

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: DMCR

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365 on Windows 11

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Structure and Framework of the Essay (EUCLID 2021, 10-11)
2. Choice of Language and Proper Use of Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 23, 25)
3. References (EUCLID 2021, 35-39)
4. Style Guides (EUCLID 2021, 44-57)
5. Authorship (EUCLID 2021, 34)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As a practicing trial lawyer for 35 years, I have written and reviewed hundreds of legal documents, including appellate briefs. I have found the information in Period 1 – both written and video - very interesting and enlightening. It reminded me of the book I recently read by Adam Grant, “*Think Again. The Power of Knowing What You Don’t Know*” (Grant 2021), the title of which is quite fitting for my overall reaction to this material. Introduction to Zotero and the use of Grammarly were helpful not only to this program but overall interactions with people and institutions in my daily life.

In this response paper, I address the proper structure of academic essay writing, the available tools for improving and verifying the usage of language and references, and the importance of the integrity of original authorship.

2) STRUCTURE AND FRAMEWORK OF THE ESSAY

At first impression, the structure seems basic and familiar. As taught in undergraduate courses, “Tell them what you are going to tell them, then tell them, then tell

them what you told them.” In other words, introduce the subject matter to be discussed (introduction), discuss the matter in detail with supporting references (body), and then conclude by summarizing (conclusion) (EUCLID 2021, 10).

However, upon further study, the details prove important. Each paragraph is expected to be virtually self-contained, starting with the topic's introductory sentence, followed by supporting evidence and analysis of that evidence, and, significantly, ending with a conclusion drawn from that evidence (EUCLID 2021, 11).

One similarity I noted between legal writing to appellate courts and academic essay writing. In appellate writing, each factual statement must have a reference to the record, and each legal argument must be rooted in legal authority with citations to statutes or case law. Similarly, in academic writing, the author is expected to cite references, not only as indicia of proper research but also to avoid plagiarism and to credit those who authored the original works (EUCLID 2021, 11).

3) CHOICE OF LANGUAGE AND PROPER USE OF PUNCTUATION

The author has a choice of American or British usage (EUCLID 2021, 25). I chose American. On a personal note, for years, I have pushed back on the American placement of a period or comma inside the quote in circumstances where such usage made no logical sense. However, on balance, I am more familiar with and thus will be using American.

The material on the use of punctuation was beneficial. The proper use of commas can change the material meaning of a sentence. Indeed, there are cases in the United States where the court's determination on the meaning of a contract turns on the placement of the comma. I was a bit puzzled, though, by the last two examples given under the heading “Using other punctuation with quotation marks” of what is proper and improper usage which appear identical, to wit: “‘The kitchen,’ he said, ‘is the heart of the home’” (EUCLID 2021, 23).

4) REFERENCES

References can be essentially divided into three categories: (1) in-text citations, (2) footnote citations, and (3) bibliography (EUCLID 2021, 35-39).

Parentheses denote in-text citations and contain the author's last name or title of the work and page number. Response papers, such as this one, utilize in-text citations. Footnote references contain the author's full name, the title of the work in italics, and the page number. Zotero is helpful with footnote citations. The bibliography, which appears at the end of the work, is a compilation of all the references used (EUCLID 2021, 38).

5) STYLE GUIDES

There are many styles available for usage with essays. EUCLID expects its students to use the *Chicago Manual of Style* (CMS), 2003, and Turabian's *Manual of Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, commonly referred to as "Turabian style," which is the Chicago style applied to research papers (EUCLID 2021, 44).

This style recommends using dictionaries (*Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary*), particular abbreviations, forms of capitalization, italics and quotation usage, page formats, and other language features for correctness and consistency (EUCLID 2021, 44-57).

6) AUTHORSHIP

For obvious moral and ethical reasons, plagiarism is frowned upon. First, it is simply wrong to misappropriate the work of another. Second, it diminishes the expected originality and creativity of the author utilizing another's work. We all build on the work, research, and ideas that preceded us. However, it is imperative that we properly credit the efforts of others we include in our work (EUCLID 2021, 34).

7) CONCLUSION

The content and format rules for academic essays are comprehensively covered in Period 1, detailing both substance and configuration rules and guides. The aides discussed, such as Zotero and Grammarly, assist the student in the proper presentation of written materials. Finally, the importance of crediting the work of others and avoiding plagiarism is emphasized.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Grant, Adam. 2021. *Think Again*. Viking.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.